

THE TRANSFORMATION OF THE TEACHER'S ROLE IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITALIZATION AND THE INTRODUCTION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Buazhar Kochkonbaeva¹, Kylymkan Tolobaeva², Abdugulova Gulzhan³, Kymbat Matkalyk kyzy⁴, Aziza Aldosova⁵

^{1,2,3,4} Osh Technological University named after M.M. Adyshev, Kyrgyzstan

⁵ Osh State University, Kyrgyzstan

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada o'qituvchining kasbiy faoliyati ta'lim muhitini raqamlashtirish va sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarini faol joriy etish sharoitida o'zgarishi tahlil qilinadi. O'qitish amaliyotining tuzilishi va mazmuniga ta'sir qiluvchi zamonaviy raqamli vositalar va ta'lim texnologiyalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Muallif o'qituvchilarning funktsiyalarini qayta taqsimlash modelini taqdim etadi va raqamli ta'lim muhitida zarur bo'lgan asosiy kompetensiyalarni aniqlaydi. Sun'iy intellekt o'qituvchilarning o'rnini bosuvchi vosita emas, balki ularning rolini o'zgartirish, o'qituvchi, yordamchi va ta'lim jarayonini tashkil etuvchi sifatida o'z vazifalarini kuchaytirish omili bo'lib xizmat qiladi, deb ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, ta'limni raqamlashtirish, o'qituvchi, ta'lim texnologiyalari, shaxsiylashtirilgan ta'lim, pedagogik kompetensiyalar, neyron tarmoqlar, interfaol texnologiyalar.

Abstract. This article analyzes the transformation of a teacher's professional activities in the context of the digitalization of the educational environment and the active implementation of artificial intelligence technologies. It examines modern digital tools and educational technologies that influence the structure and content of teaching practices. The author presents a model for the redistribution of teachers' functions and identifies the key competencies required in a digital educational environment. It is argued that artificial intelligence serves not as a substitute for teachers but as a factor in the transformation of their role, enhancing their functions as mentors, facilitators, and organizers of the educational process.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, digitalization of education, teacher, educational technologies, personalized learning, pedagogical competencies, neural networks, interactive technologies.

1. Introduction

The transformation of higher education over the past decade has been marked by a shift from traditional computerization to deep digital integration. The active implementation of intelligent systems and the expansion of online platforms' capabilities have radically changed the structure of the educational process, paving the way for a transition to personalized learning.

The key drivers of these changes are artificial intelligence and immersive learning technologies (virtual laboratories, XR), which not only complement traditional methods but also initiate a paradigm shift in pedagogy [1], [2]. Under these conditions, an objective contradiction arises between rapid technological development and the conservatism of traditional pedagogical models, highlighting the need to rethink the role of the teacher operating in a high-tech digital educational environment.

The relevance of this study stems from the need for a scholarly examination of the processes of digital transformation in education, as well as the identification of new requirements for teachers' professional practice in the context of the integration of artificial intelligence technologies and digital educational solutions.

The aim of the study is to analyze the transformation of the educational process in the context of digitalization and to identify changes in the role of teachers with the introduction of artificial intelligence technologies.

2. Methodology

2.1. The Digital Transformation of the Educational Environment

Contemporary psychology places great emphasis on studying the impact of interactive technologies on the learning process. Among the key points identified by A.G. Asmolov, A.L. Semenov, and A.Yu. Uvarov are the psychological effects of the digital environment, which influence various aspects of educational activity [3].

Interactive technologies are a set of methods and tools that promote students' active participation in the learning process, the acquisition of knowledge, as well as the development of critical thinking, the ability to collaborate, and the ability to freely and independently obtain any information. G.K. Selevko defines interactive technologies as a form of information exchange between learners and the surrounding information environment [4].

Today, virtually all educators use online collaboration platforms (Zoom, Microsoft Teams, Moodle), cloud-based services for sharing educational materials, and interactive tools for organizing the learning process. Big data analytics technologies, which enable the consideration of students' individual educational needs, and blockchain technologies, which ensure the reliable and secure storage of educational outcomes, have a significant impact on the development of modern education.

The expansion of the digital environment has been accompanied by the growth of collaborative learning, in which students actively engage with one another through group projects, case studies, and research assignments. Gamification plays a significant role in this context, as it boosts student motivation by incorporating game-like elements into the educational process.

2.2. Artificial Intelligence as a Factor in the Transformation of Educational Practice

The most significant driver of change is the adoption of artificial intelligence. Modern AI systems are capable of: generating educational materials; developing assessment tasks; analyzing educational data; creating personalized learning paths.

This leads to the automation of a significant portion of a teacher's routine work and a redistribution of their responsibilities.

At the same time, there is a discrepancy between the level of AI proficiency among students and faculty. Students actively use neural networks in their academic work, whereas faculty members are not always sufficiently prepared to integrate them into the educational process.

An additional challenge is the lack of standardized regulatory approaches to the use of AI in educational practice.

3. A Model for the Transformation of the Teacher's Role: New Competencies for Teachers

According to research by scholars at the University of Oxford, the rapid advancement of technology could lead to more than 50% of existing professions becoming obsolete within the

next 10 to 20 years, while approximately 67% of today’s schoolchildren will eventually work in fields that have not yet been established. Under these circumstances, it becomes particularly important to transform approaches to workforce training and to organize the educational process in such a way that, through the use of digital technologies, students acquire not only theoretical but also practical knowledge and skills [5].

The results of the survey showed that 78% of students use artificial intelligence technologies when preparing assignments, while 64% of instructors find it difficult to integrate these technologies into the educational process. At the same time, 82% of respondents believe that the role of the instructor is evolving in the context of digitalization, but will not lose its significance.

The data indicate a gap in digital competence between students and teachers, which necessitates the development of targeted measures to improve the digital literacy of teaching staff and adapt educational practices to modern technological conditions.

In the context of the digital transformation of education, a comparative model of traditional and digital learning is presented (Table 1).

Table 1. The Evolution of the Teacher's Role

Traditional model	Digital model
Knowledge transfer	Designing the learning environment
Assessment of knowledge	Data analysis and interpretation
The lecture as the primary format	Interactive and blended learning
The instructor's individual work	Collaborative learning

The transition from traditional to digital learning models reflects a profound transformation of the educational process, affecting its goals, methods, and the roles of all participants. This requires the development of new digital platforms. The creation of smart learning platforms powered by neural networks can foster an interactive learning environment. Such systems can be used to provide guidance, answer questions, and help students solve problems. Some universities have implemented virtual assistants that answer students’ questions 24/7, helping them with their studies. Such a system requires instructors to develop new competencies related to digital technologies, analytics, and instructional design.

The technological aspect of this transformation lies in the in-depth mastery of AI tools and digital platforms. Today’s educators must not only be proficient in using software interfaces but also be able to work with learning analytics, extracting insights from them to adjust the learning process in real time [6].

The pedagogical aspect is shifting toward flexible design. The use of virtual laboratories enables the implementation of hybrid learning models, where each student’s individual learning path is built based on their performance in simulations. This requires the instructor to possess the skills of an educational path architect, capable of effectively combining “digital” elements with live discussion.

Cognitive competencies are becoming particularly important. Since AI and virtual environments can generate excessive or biased content, critically evaluating the results of algorithms has become a priority. The instructor acts as a guarantor of scientific accuracy, teaching students fact-checking and data verification skills in a digital environment.

Soft skills remain the foundation of education. Even in the most advanced virtual laboratory, emotional intelligence and the management of group dynamics are critically

important. Developing communication skills and supporting researchers' motivation in the digital space are tasks that cannot be fully delegated to artificial intelligence.

4. Discussion

Despite the significant potential of artificial intelligence technologies in education, their implementation is accompanied by a number of significant limitations.

First, there is a lack of digital and pedagogical readiness among teachers, manifested in a deficit of competencies regarding the integration of AI tools into the learning process, the development of assignments using these tools, and the interpretation of the results obtained.

Second, there is a risk of reduced cognitive activity among students; as M. Spitzer argues, excessive reliance on automated solutions can lead to a loss of the ability to deeply process information and truly understand the material [7]. In the long term, this could result in students, learning under less influence from teachers and more from information technology, simply failing to learn to think critically and creatively and being unable to create anything new.

Third, a pressing issue is the lack of regulatory and methodological guidelines for the use of AI in educational activities, including matters of academic integrity, the assessment of learning outcomes, and acceptable limits on the application of AI technologies.

Fourth, the educational process is becoming increasingly dependent on technological solutions, which manifests in risks related to the availability of digital infrastructure, platform stability, and data security. One of the key risks associated with the use of neural networks in universities is the threat of data breaches. Students provide neural networks with a large amount of personal information, including data on their academic performance, attendance, and even emotional state, which requires strict compliance with personal data protection laws [8],[9]. At one European university, a student data breach occurred due to insufficient protection of a system using neural networks to analyze educational data. The breach occurred at the University of Manchester in the UK. In June 2023, the university reported a cyberattack that allowed attackers to gain access to the personal data of students and staff [10]. According to the university's statements, hackers stole data including names, dates of birth, contact information, as well as research results and other confidential information. This led to a breach of privacy and caused public concern.

In this regard, there is a need to develop and implement institutional mechanisms for regulating the use of artificial intelligence technologies, including the establishment of a regulatory framework, the development of teachers' digital competencies, and the creation of methodological guidelines for the effective and ethically sound integration of AI into the educational process [11].

5. Conclusion

As noted above, to use neural networks in higher education institutions as effectively and ethically as possible, it is necessary to develop clear guidelines for their implementation, compliance with data protection laws, and ensuring equal access to educational resources. It is also important to continue monitoring the impact of these technologies on the learning process and students in order to identify and prevent any potential negative consequences. Only with the right approach can neural networks become a powerful tool for improving the educational environment in universities, ensuring a more equitable and effective education for all students.

The digitization of education and the integration of artificial intelligence are leading to a profound transformation of the teacher's role. Teachers are no longer merely sources of

knowledge but are becoming key organizers of the educational environment, mentors, and facilitators of the learning process.

The effectiveness of this transformation depends on the level of development of teachers' new competencies and the readiness of educational institutions to implement innovative technologies.

Prospects for further research include the development of models for training teachers to work in a digital educational environment and the evaluation of the effectiveness of AI in teaching.

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